

ISSUES OF ORGANIZATIONAL LEGAL DEVELOPMENT OF
THE PROBATION SERVICE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation: In this article author reveals the legal framework for ensuring the activities of the probation service, which has recently become one of the most important participants in the process of resocialization and correction of criminals in Uzbekistan. In particular, the laws and by-laws regarding the legal regulation of the probation service are analyzed in detail, from the moment of gaining Independence to the present day. The article notes that some serious gaps and shortcomings in the legislation in practice have a negative impact on the effectiveness of the work of probation officers. In the article, the author substantiates the need for the adoption of the Law “On Probation” to improve the legal status of the probation service and further regulate its activities, presents relevant scientific and practical proposals and recommendations.

Key words: probation service, crime, international standards, judicial system, national legislation.

Intraduction: In our country, a wide range of measures are being implemented to morally correct persons who committed crimes, to re-educate them in close cooperation with the public without separating them from society. In particular, as a result of the measures taken to reform the system of internal affairs bodies, early prevention of offenses and the fight against crime, taking into account advanced foreign experience and international standards, the activities of the Probation Service were established.

The legal basis for the execution of criminal penalties that carry out tasks specific to the functions of probation, in particular not related to imprisonment, is our independence in our country.

It began to be created from 1992-2001. At this time, the law "on administrative control of internal affairs bodies over persons discharged from penitentiary institutions" and the Criminal executive code of the Republic of Uzbekistan were adopted in 1997.

Methods: It should be noted that the law "on amendments and additions to the criminal, criminal-procedural and administrative-liability codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the liberalization of criminal penalties", adopted on August 29, 2001, served as a kind of focal point in the liberalization of the judicial-legal system, including criminal, criminal-procedural legislation¹.

Article 4 of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 407 "on internal affairs bodies" dated September 16, 2016 establishes the organization of Public Order and Public Security and the execution of criminal penalties from the main areas of activity of internal affairs bodies.

The largest and large-scale reforms in the field of human rights and judicial law in Uzbekistan are carried out by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is no exaggeration to say that Mirziyoyev began with a strategy of action on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, approved by Decree No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017. The decree provides for a comprehensive study, analysis and assessment of the organizational and legal foundations and effectiveness of the activities of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, first of all, the need to improve the activities of penitentiary structures².

As a continuation of the reforms in the judicial system, the Probation Service

¹ Tajikhanov B.U. Uzbekistan: Liberalization and the main directions of legal policy.-T.: 2002.-pp. 60-63.

²Electronic source. Year of introduction: <https://www.Lex.uz>

was established by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2018 No. 4006 PQ.

Based on this decision, it is established that the Probation Service carries out the control of persons who are in the account in seven directions (correctional labor, deprivation of a certain right, restriction of Liberty, conditionally convicted, compulsory public works, conditionally released from penal institutions and minors).

Also, on the need for legal support of the activities of the Probation Service of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev by Decree No. 6155 PD on February 3, 2021 "2017 — Paragraph 30 of the state program on the implementation of the strategy of actions in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021 at the "year of support for youth and strengthening public health" set a number of tasks for the further improvement of punishment and Probation Service with the widespread introduction of international standards and humanitarian principle.

The resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on additional measures to effectively organize the activities of the Probation Service of internal affairs bodies" dated February 14, 2020 No. 84 established the introduction of the procedure for limiting the withdrawal of persons under probation from the territory of the Republic.

In paragraph 7 of this decision, the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, until December 1, 2020, together with the State Security Service, the prosecutor general's office, established the introduction of a draft normative legal Act Providing for limiting their exit from the territory of the Republic in cases where those under control arbitrarily left their place of residence for the

Paragraph 1 of the "plan of measures for the more effective organization of the activities of the Probation Service of the internal affairs bodies in 2020-2021

"approved by this decision provides for the introduction of a procedure that provides for limiting their exit from the territory of the Republic in cases where those under control arbitrarily left their place of residence in order.

On the basis of this decision, the following measures are being implemented³:

- introduction of a procedure that provides for limiting their exit from the territory of the Republic in cases where those under control arbitrarily leave the place of residence in order to evade administrative control;

- implementation of the procedure for stimulating employees of probation units (groups) at the expense of sources of the Fund for the development of probation services;

- introduction of the procedure for internships in probation units (groups) of students studying in the field of psychology in the relevant higher educational institutions;

- Implementation of a system for professional development of employees of the Probation Service at the Institute for advanced training of the Ministry of internal affairs;

- introduction of special topics on the study of socio-psychological portrait of those under supervision in educational programs of higher educational institutions in legal directions;

- Organization of business trips of employees of the Probation Service to developed foreign countries in order to pass the internship, study foreign legislation;

- strengthening research work on probation activities;

³ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 84 of February 14, 2020 "on additional measures to effectively organize the activities of the Probation Service of internal affairs bodies" / / national database of information of legislation, dated 14.02.2020., 09/20/84/0167-issue.

-Organization of talk shows, social rollers, special shows, articles, speeches and broadcasts on bringing to the general public the essence of the work carried out by the Probation Service and its territorial units.

The resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on organizational measures to ensure the effectiveness of the activities of penitentiary institutions associated with imprisonment" dated March 5, 2020 No. 128 established the application of electronic bracelets to the activities of the Probation Service.

With this decision, the "program for equipping penal institutions of the type of imprisonment in 2020 with video surveillance devices and personal video recorders (bodi-cameras) and the implementation of electronic bracelets in the practice of the Probation Service" was approved. According to the program, in 2020, it was established that 3000 units will be implemented, and in the coming years, electronic bracelets will be applied to the activities of the Probation Service based on the need.

In paragraph 5 of this decision, the costs associated with the implementation of electronic bracelets in the practice of the Probation Service are determined by the budget funds allocated by the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan on The based calculations of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the centralized fund of the Main Directorate for

Results: Projects in the program of these measures are provided for financing at the expense of state budget funds allocated to the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, extrabudgetary funds of the ministry and other sources not prohibited by legislative acts⁴.

⁴ Estimated cost of electronic bracelets required for the implementation and monitoring of the practice of using electronic bracelets for control over the behavior of persons under the supervision of the Probation Service and the estimated cost of economic accounting for server and hardware supply 1 unit cost of electronic bracelet – \$ 250, (the number of bracelets required to be purchased is 3,000 pieces- \$ 750,000), the license price for 1 piece of bracelet Is \$ 100 (\$ 300,000 for a total license), \$ 400,000 for devices needed by server and hardware, and the software Price Is \$ 1,450,00 for a free total total price of \$ 1,450,000.

In accordance with Appendix 1 of the order of the minister of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 07, 2018 No. 316 "on measures to organize the activities of the Probation Service", the regulation on the birth of the Probation Service under the Main Directorate for the execution of punishment and

Organizational structure of the probationary service in accordance with Appendix 2 and in accordance with Appendix 3, the model regulation on territorial units of the Probation Service was approved, and the Organization of activities of the Probation Service was established by Orders No. 379 on amendments and additions to this order on November 11, 2019.

In addition, on the order of the minister of Internal Affairs dated July 27, 2017 No. 157 "on the organization of the execution of punishments in the sphere of deprivation of a certain right, correctional work and restriction of liberty, as well as on the procedure for exercising control over conditionally convicted persons", the bodies providing for the execution of punishment in the general, the obligations of the administration of the organization, as well as the authorized bodies that have issued permission to engage in a particular type of activity, are established .

However, taking into account the large number of relevant underground legislation regulating the activities of the Probation Service in Uzbekistan, in turn, the absence of the legal status of the Probation Service in criminal Executive law, the fact that legal grounds in the activities of the internal affairs bodies are not regulated by law, it is advisable to adopt the "probation law", which regulates

The need to adopt the "probation law"

The concept of improving the criminal executive legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021. (Approved by resolution PD-4006 of November 7, 2018) 1.2, 1.7, 1.9, 2.2, 2.4, 2.9-the clauses set out within the framework of a number of tasks for the legal regulation of the probationary sphere.

Finally, the task of the administration of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan to develop a draft of a single normative legal act regulating relations in the field of probation, established in the order of April 7, 2021.⁵

The law covers the determination of the purpose, status, function and main priorities of the Probation Service, determination of the rights and obligations of participants in legal relations in this direction and martyrs serving punishments not related to imprisonment, as well as the establishment of a system for their control, as well as ensuring their interaction and cooperation with state authorities, organizations and

Through this law, the criminal executive ensures the improvement of the effectiveness of the legal regulation of relations in the field of law, as well as the implementation of the norms of international law into national legislation.

Researchers and scientists in this regard are also approving such an opinion. In Particular, M.M. According to Haydarov's approach, this law allows legal regulation of the following issues related to probation: the legal status of persons under probation control; procedure for controlling and controlling the activities of probation bodies and their powers; procedure for implementing probation control; means of moral correction of persons under probation control and the procedure for their application; the procedure for the implementation of preventive measures to identify and prevent the risk of committing a social re-crime of persons under probation control the procedure and conditions for transferring convicts to the framework of the competence of probation bodies.⁶

Also M.M. Haydarov noted the feasibility of legal regulation of these areas on the basis of a single code, since the performance of punishment and probation activities are inextricably linked, and proposed to call the Criminal executive codec

⁵ 27.07.17 y. Command number 157 in

^{6*} Deputy head of the Department of criminal and criminal Executive law M.M. Khaydarov, "Academy on the way to improve the system of training qualified personnel for internal affairs bodies" Academy of the Department of internal affairs-2019. Materials of the international scientific and practical conference. Issue-38. 222-page.

of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition "code of punishment and Probation of the Republic of Uzbekistan"⁷.

Researcher Sh.A.Hozhaev it is necessary to adopt the law "on probation control", which regulates organizational issues in the activities of probation bodies, the participation of the public in this process. In the draft new edition of the Criminal Code, it is necessary to include the chapter "probation measures."⁸

Discussion: In our opinion, the adoption of the law will serve to eliminate legal gaps and contradictions in the probation system, to implement international standards and advanced foreign experience, taking into account national characteristics and conditions, as well as to eliminate emerging issues in the practice of probation.

The ultimate result is the creation of an effective and effective system for ensuring the protection of human rights, freedoms and legitimate interests, ensuring the safety of the individual, society and the state, the formation of law-abiding behavior in persons under probation control and a respectful attitude to the rules of conduct in society, their social adaptation and the Prevention of.

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⁷ In that source

⁸ Sh.A.Khodzhaev / / "prospects for the introduction of the probation Institute in the criminal legislation of Uzbekistan".

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